

CODEN [USA]: IAJPB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ANALYTICAL METHOD FOR SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF
OXYCODONE AND NALTREXONE IN PHARMACEUTICAL
FORMULATION BY RP-HPLC****S.Prasanti¹, I.Spoorthi², Y.Chaitanya Kumar³, P.Naga Manikanta⁴**

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Abstract:

AIM: The main aim of the present study is development of accurate, precise, sensitive, selective, reproducible and rapid analytical technique for cost effective simultaneous estimation of Oxycodone and Naltrexone.

Background: A simple, accurate and precise HPLC method for simultaneous determination of Oxycodone and Naltrexone in pure and tablet dosage form has been developed.

Aim: To develop and validate analytical method for simultaneous estimation of Oxycodone and Naltrexone in pharmaceutical formulation by RP-HPLC.

Materials and Methods: HPLC of Waters (Model: Alliance 2695) with Phenomenex Luna C18 (4.6 mm I.D. × 250 mm, 5 μm) column was used for chromatographic separation. It contains waters injector and PDA Detector (Deuterium). Mobile phase consists of Acetonitrile : Water (75:25% v/v) and flow rate adjusted was 1ml/min. Wavelength selected for detection was 285nm and injection volume was 10 μl.

Results and discussion: By using the developed method, retention time of Oxycodone and Naltrexone was found to be 3.2min and 5.4min respectively. The method has been validated for linearity, accuracy and precision. Linearity of Oxycodone and Naltrexone were in the range of 20–100 μg/ml and 10–50 μg/ml respectively. The percentage recoveries obtained for Oxycodone and Naltrexone were found to be in range of 99.3 – 99.6% LOD and LOQ were found to be 5.0 μg/ml and 15.2 μg/ml for Oxycodone 3.7 and 11.4 μg/ml for Naltrexone.

Keywords: Oxycodone, Naltrexone, Simultaneous Estimation, RP- HPLC

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Please cite this article in press S. Prasanti et al Analytical Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Oxycodone and Naltrexone in Pharmaceutical Formulation by RP-HPLC, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(07).

1. INTRODUCTION:

In the modern pharmaceutical industry, high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) is the major and integral analytical tool applied in all stages of drug discovery, development and production. It is ideal for the analysis of many drugs in both dosage forms and biological fluids due to its simplicity, high specificity and good sensitivity.

High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) is a technique that has arisen from the application to liquid chromatography the use of an instrumentation that was originally developed for gas chromatography. High Pressure Liquid Chromatography was developed in the mid-1970 and was improved with the development of column packing material and the additional convenience of on-line detectors. The various components of HPLC are pumps (solvent delivery system), mixing unit, gradient controller and solvent degasser, injector (manual or automatic), guard column, analytical columns, detectors, recorders and/or integrators. Recent models are equipped with computers and software for data acquisition and processing. The mobile phase in HPLC refers to the solvent being continuously applied to the column or stationary phase at a flow rate of 1-5 cm³/min. The mobile phase acts as a carrier for the sample solution. The chemical interactions of the mobile phase and sample with the column determine the degree of migration and separation of components contained in the sample. The mobile phase can be altered in order to manipulate the interactions of the sample and the stationary phase.

1.1.1 Types of Chromatography

1. Normal-phase chromatography

Mechanism: Retention by interaction with the polar surface of the stationary phase with polar parts of the sample molecules.

Stationary phase: SiO₂, Al₂O₃, -NH₂, -CN, -Diol, -NO₂, etc.

Mobile phase: Heptane, hexane, cyclohexane, CHCl₃, CH₂Cl₂, dioxane, methanol, etc.

Application: Separation of non-ionic, non-polar to medium polar substances. Disadvantage: Lack of reproducibility of retention times as water or protic organic solvents change the hydration state of the silica or alumina chromatographic media.

2. Reversed-phase chromatography

Mechanism: Retention by interaction of the stationary phase's non-polar hydrocarbon chain with non-polar parts of the sample molecules.

Stationary phase: n-octadecyl (RP-18), n-octyl (RP-8), ethyl (RP-2), phenyl, (CH₂)_n-CN, (CH₂)_n-diol, etc.

Mobile phase: Methanol, acetonitrile, water, buffer (sometimes with additives of THF or Dioxane), etc.

3. Reversed-phase ion-pair chromatography

Mechanism: Ionic sample molecules are ionically bound to an ion-pair reagent. The ion-pair reagent contains an unpolar part suitable for interaction with the unpolar hydrocarbon chain of the stationary phase.

Stationary phase: Reversed phase materials (RP-18, RP-8, CN), etc.

Mobile phase: Methanol, acetonitrile, buffer with added ion-pair reagent in the concentration range of 0.001 to 0.01 M, etc.

4. Ion-exchange chromatography

Mechanism: Retention of reversible ionic bonds on charged groups of the stationary phase

Stationary phase:

	Strong	Weak
Cation exchanger	SO ₃ ⁻	COO ⁻
Anion exchanger	NR ₃ ⁺	NHR ₂ ⁺

Mobile phase: Aqueous buffer systems.

Application: Separation of substances which can form ions such as inorganic ions, organic acids, organic bases, proteins, nucleic acids.

1.1.2 Advantages of HPLC

- 1) It provides specific, sensitive and precise method for analysis of the different complicated sample.
- 2) There is ease of sample preparation and sample introduction.
- 3) There is speed of analysis.
- 4) The analysis by HPLC is specific, accurate and precise.
- 5) It offers advantage over gas chromatography in analysis of many polar, ionic substances, high molecular weight substances, metabolic products and thermolabile as well as nonvolatile substances.

1.1.3 Applications of HPLC

- a) Natural Products: HPLC is an ideal method for the estimation of various components in plant extracts which resemble in structure and thus demand a specific and very sensitive method e.g., analysis of digitalis, cinchona, liquorice, and ergot extracts.
- b) Stability studies: HPLC is now used for ascertaining the stability of various pharmaceuticals. With HPLC the analysis of the various degradation products can be done and thus stability indicating HPLC systems have been developed.
- c) Bioassays and its complementation: Complex molecules as antibiotics and peptide hormones are mainly analysed by bioassay which suffer from high cost, necessity replicates, poor precision and length of time required. Also bioassay gives an overall estimate of potency and gives no guidance about the

composition. Thus HPLC can be used to complement bioassays and give an activity profile. It has been used for analysis of chloramphenicol, penicillins, clotrimoxazole, sulfas and peptides hormones.

1.1.4 Instrumentation

Figure 1. Diagram of HPLC Instrument^[3]

The basic components of HPLC are: [4-8]

1. Pumping System
2. Sample Introduction Device
3. Chromatographic Column
4. Detector
5. Data handling Device

1. Pumping System: The HPLC pump is very important component of the system. It delivers the constant flow of the mobile phase or phases so that the separation of the components of the mixture occur in a reasonable time. Its performance directly affects retention time, reproducibility and detector sensitivity. Three main types of pumps are used in HPLC to propel the liquid mobile phase through the system are as under;

a. Displacement pump: It produces a flow that tends to independent of viscosity and backpressure and also output is pulse free. But it possesses limited capacity (250 ml).

b. Reciprocating pump: It has small internal volume (35 to 400 μ l). It has high output pressure (up to 10,000 psi) and constant flow rates. But it produces a pulsed flow.

c. Pneumatic or constant pressure pump: They are pulse free, suffer from limited capacity as well as a dependence of flow rate on solvent viscosity and column back pressure. They are limited to pressure less than 2000 psi.

There are two type of elution process, i.e. isocratic and gradient

d) HPLC has also been used in the cosmetic industry for quality control of various cosmetics.

Isocratic: In this system, the things are kept constant throughout the run. In the case of pumping of mobile phase, the mobile phase composition is kept constant throughout the run. The nominal flow rate accuracy required is $\pm 1\%$ of the set flow

Gradient: There is some change purposely incorporated during the particular sample run to achieve a better or/and faster separation. In case of pumping mobile phase, the composition of mobile phase is continuously varied during the particular run. The gradient accuracy of $\pm 1\%$ of the step gradient composition is typical.

2. Sample Introducing Device

It is not possible to use direct syringe injection on column like GC, as the inlet pressure in LC is too high. Insertion of the sample onto the pressurized column must be as a narrow plug so that the peak broadening attributable to this step is negligible. The injection system itself should have no dead (void) volume. There are three important ways of introducing the sample into injection port.

a. Loop injection: In which, a fixed amount of volume is introduced by making use of fixed volume loop injector.

b. Valve injection: In which, a variable volume is introduced by making use of an injection valve.

c. On column injection: In which, a variable volume is introduced by means of a syringe through a septum.

3. Chromatographic Column

Column is a heart of chromatography. The column is usually made up of heavy glass or stainless steel tubing to withstand high pressure. The columns are usually 10-30 cm long and 4-10 mm inside diameter containing stationary phase at particle diameter of 25

μm or less. Columns with an internal diameter of 5 mm give good results because of compromise between efficiency, sample capacity, and the amount of packing and solvent required.

Figure 2. Different Types of Columns[3]

Column packing:

The packing used in modern HPLC consists of small, rigid particles having a narrow particle size distribution. There are three main types of column packing in HPLC.

a. Porous, polymeric beds: Porous, polymeric beds based on styrene divinyl benzene co-polymers used for ion exchange and size exclusion chromatography. For analytical purpose these have now been replaced by silica based, packing which are more efficient and more stable.

b. Porous layer beds: Consisting of a thin shell (1-3 μm) of silica or modified silica on an spherical inert core (e.g. Glass). After the development of totally porous micro particulate packings, these have not been used in HPLC.

c. Totally Porous silica particles (dia. < 10 μm): These packing have widely been used for analytical HPLC in recent years. Particles of diameter > 20 μm are usually dry packed. While particles of diameter < 20 μm are slurry packed in which particles are suspended on a suitable solvent and the slurry so obtained is driven into the column under pressure.

4. Detector

The function of the detector in HPLC is to monitor the mobile phase as it merges from the column. There are several detectors available in the market. However UV Visible detector, photo diode array detector, fluorescence detector, conductometric and coulometric detector are more commonly used. The new ELSD detector is proving to be important detector, while the MS detector is outstanding. Detectors are usually of two types:

a. Bulk property detectors: It compares overall changes in a physical property of the mobile phase

with and without an eluting solute e.g. refractive index, dielectric constant or density.

b. Solute property detectors: It responds to a physical property of the solute, which is not exhibited by the pure mobile phase e.g. UV absorbance, fluorescence or diffusion current.

5. Data handling Device

Computer-based system that controls all components of HPLC instrument (eluent composition (mixing of different solvents); temperature, injection sequence, etc.) and acquires data from the detector and monitors system performance (continuous monitoring of the mobile phase composition, temperature, back pressure, etc.)

DRUG PROFILE:

Drug : Oxycodone
Synonym : Oxycodonum, Eukodal

Drug category : Central Nervous System
Depressants

Structure :

Chemical name/ Nomenclature / IUPAC Name :
(5R,9R,13S,14S)-4,5 α -epoxy-14-hydroxy-3-methoxy-17-methylmorphinan-6-one

Molecular Formula : C₁₈H₂₁NO₄

Molecular Weight : 315.3636 gm/mole.

PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES:

Description(Physical State) : Solid

Solubility: sparingly soluble in ethanol (95), slightly soluble in acetic anhydride, and practically insoluble in diethyl ether.

Storage Conditions: Store oxycodone at 77 degrees F (25 degrees C). Brief storage at temperatures between 59 and 86 degrees F (15 and 30 degrees C) is permitted. Store away from light, heat, and moisture. Do not store in the bathroom.

Melting point : 219 °C

pKa(strongest acidic) : 13.56

Log P : 0.3

PHARMACOKINETIC PROPERTIES:

Bioavailability : 60–87 %

Half-life : 2-3 hrs

Absorption : Well absorbed with an oral route

Volume of Distribution : 2.6 L

Protein binding : 45 %

Metabolism : Hepatic

Excretion : Urine (83%)

Route Of Administration : Oral

Adverse effects/Side effects : The effects of oxycodone include pain relief, euphoria, anxiolysis, feelings of relaxation, and respiratory depression .

Common side effects of oxycodone include constipation (23%), nausea (23%), vomiting (12%), somnolence (23%), dizziness (13%), itching (13%), dry mouth (6%), and sweating (5%).

Less common side effects (experienced by less than 5% of patients) include loss of appetite, nervousness, abdominal pain, diarrhea, urine retention, dyspnea, and hiccups.

PHARMACODYNAMICS: Oxycodone, a semisynthetic opiate agonist derived from the opioid alkaloid, thebaine, is similar to other phenanthrene derivatives such as hydrocodone and morphine. Oxycodone is available in combination with aspirin or acetaminophen to control pain and restless leg and Tourette syndromes.

Mechanism of action: Oxycodone acts as a weak agonist at mu, kappa, and delta opioid receptors within the central nervous system (CNS). Oxycodone primarily affects mu-type opioid receptors, which are coupled with G-protein receptors and function as modulators, both positive and negative, of synaptic transmission via G-proteins that activate effector proteins. Binding of the opiate stimulates the

exchange of GTP for GDP on the G-protein complex. As the effector system is adenylate cyclase and cAMP located at the inner surface of the plasma membrane, opioids decrease intracellular cAMP by inhibiting adenylate cyclase. Subsequently, the release of nociceptive neurotransmitters such as substance P, GABA, dopamine, acetylcholine, and noradrenaline is inhibited. Opioids such as oxycodone also inhibit the release of vasopressin, somatostatin, insulin, and glucagon. Opioids close N-type voltage-operated calcium channels (kappa-receptor agonist) and open calcium-dependent inwardly rectifying potassium channels (mu and delta receptor agonist). This results in hyperpolarization and reduced neuronal excitability.

Therapeutic efficacy/ Indications: For the treatment of diarrhoea, pulmonary oedema and for the relief of moderate to moderately severe pain.

Contraindications:

Oxycontin is contraindicated in patients with:

- Significant respiratory depression.
- Acute or severe bronchial asthma in an unmonitored setting or in the absence of resuscitative equipment.
- Known or suspected paralytic ileus and gastrointestinal obstruction.

INTERACTIONS:

Drug interactions:

- The risk or severity of adverse effects can be increased when Atropine is combined with Oxycodone.
- Doxylamine may increase the central nervous system depressant (CNS depressant) activities of Oxycodone.

Food interactions:

- Take without regard to meals. Avoid alcohol.

NALTREXONE

Drug category: Central Nervous System Depressants

Structure :

IUPAC Name : (1S,5R,13R,17S)-4-(cyclopropylmethyl)-10,17-dihydroxy-12-oxa-4-

azapentacyclo[9.6.1.0^{1,13}.0^{5,17}.0^{7,18}]octadeca-7(18),8,10-trien-14-one

Molecular Formula :
C₂₀H₂₃NO₄

Molecular Weight : 341.401
g/mol

Official Pharmacopoeia : British Pharmacopoeia, United States Pharmacopoeia, Indian Pharmacopoeia, European pharmacopoeia

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES

Description : Derivative of noroxymorphone that is the N-cyclopropylmethyl congener of naloxone. It is a narcotic antagonist that is effective orally, longer lasting and more potent than naloxone, and has been proposed for the treatment of heroin addiction. The FDA has approved naltrexone for the treatment of alcohol dependence.

Solubility : water solubility

Dosage : 50 mg

Melting point : 169 °C (336 °F)

pKa(strongest basic) : 11.54

Log p value : 1.92

PHARMACOKINETICS

Route Of Administration : Oral

Bioavailability : 5–40%

Half-life : 4 h (naltrexone), 13 h (6-β-naltrexol)

Absorption : Although well absorbed orally, naltrexone is subject to significant first pass metabolism with oral bioavailability estimates ranging from 5 to 40%.

Volume of Distribution : 1350 L

Protein binding : 21%

Metabolism : hepatic

Excretion : Urine

PHARMACODYNAMICS

Mechanism of action : Naltrexone is a pure opiate antagonist and has little or no agonist activity. The mechanism of action of naltrexone in alcoholism is not understood; however, involvement

of the endogenous opioid system is suggested by preclinical data. Naltrexone is thought to act as a competitive antagonist at μ , κ , and δ receptors in the CNS, with the highest affinity for the μ receptor. Naltrexone competitively binds to such receptors and may block the effects of endogenous opioids. This leads to the antagonization of most of the subjective and objective effects of opiates, including respiratory depression, miosis, euphoria, and drug craving. The major metabolite of naltrexone, 6-β-naltrexol, is also an opiate antagonist and may contribute to the antagonistic activity of the drug.

Indications : Used as an adjunct to a medically supervised behaviour modification program in the maintenance of opiate cessation in individuals who were formerly physically dependent on opiates and who have successfully undergone detoxification. Also used for the management of alcohol dependence in conjunction with a behavioural modification program.

Adverse reactions: diarrhea and abdominal cramping, liver damage

Contraindications : Naltrexone (50 mg per day) should not be used by persons with acute hepatitis or liver failure, or those with recent opioid use (typically 7–10 days).

INTERACTIONS

Drug interactions : Some products that may interact with this drug include: cough medication (e.g., dextromethorphan), disulfiram, diarrhea medication (e.g., diphenoxylate), narcotic medication (e.g., codeine, hydrocodone, propoxyphene), thioridazine.

Food interactions : Naltrexone may cause liver problems, and using it with other medications that can also affect the liver such as ethanol may increase that risk. You should avoid or limit the use of alcohol while being treated with these medications.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

INSTRUMENTS USED

Table 1: Instruments used

S.No	Instruments and Glassware	Model
1	HPLC	WATERS Alliance 2695 separation module, Software: Empower 2, 996 PDA detector.
2	pH meter	LabIndia
3	Weighing machine	Sartorius
4	Volumetric flasks	Borosil
5	Pipettes and Burettes	Borosil
6	Beakers	Borosil
7	Digital ultra sonicator	Labman

CHEMICALS USED:

Table 2: chemicals used

S.No	Chemical	Brand names
1	Oxycodone(Pure)	Sura labs
2	Naltrexone(Pure)	Sura labs
3	Water and Methanol for HPLC	LICHROSOLV (MERCK)
4	Acetonitrile for HPLC	Merck

HPLC METHOD DEVELOPMENT:**TRAILS****Preparation of standard solution:**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Oxycodone and Naltrexone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Methanol and sonicate to dissolve and removal of air completely and make volume up to the mark with the same Methanol.

Further pipette 0.6ml of the above Oxycodone and 0.3ml of the Naltrexone stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Diluent.

Procedure:

Inject the samples by changing the chromatographic conditions and record the chromatograms, note the conditions of proper peak elution for performing validation parameters as per ICH guidelines.

Mobile Phase Optimization:

Initially the mobile phase tried was Methanol: Water, Acetonitrile: Water with varying proportions. Finally, the mobile phase was optimized to Acetonitrile and water in proportion 75:25 v/v respectively.

Optimization of Column:

The method was performed with various columns like C18 column, X- bridge column, Xterra. Phenomenex Luna C18 (4.6 x 150mm, 5µm) was found to be ideal as it gave good peak shape and resolution at 1ml/min flow.

VALIDATION**PREPARATION OF MOBILE PHASE:****Preparation of mobile phase:**

Accurately measured 750ml (75%) of HPLC Acetonitrile and 250ml of Water (25%) were mixed and degassed in a digital ultrasonicator for 10 minutes and then filtered through 0.45 µ filter under vacuum filtration.

Diluent Preparation:

The Mobile phase was used as the diluent.

VALIDATION PARAMETERS**Procedure:**

Inject the three replicate injections of standard and sample solutions and calculate the assay by using formula:

%ASSAY =

$$\frac{\text{Sample area}}{\text{Standard area}} \times \frac{\text{Weight of standard}}{\text{Dilution of standard}} \times \frac{\text{Dilution of sample}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times \frac{\text{Purity}}{100} \times \frac{\text{Weight of tablet}}{\text{Label claim}} \times 100$$

SYSTEM SUITABILITY

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Oxycodone and Naltrexone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.6ml of the above Oxycodone and 0.3ml of the Naltrexone stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Diluent.

Procedure:

The standard solution was injected for five times and measured the area for all five injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of five replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

SPECIFICITY STUDY OF DRUG:**Preparation of Standard Solution:**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Oxycodone and Naltrexone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.6ml of the above Oxycodone and 0.3ml of the Naltrexone stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Diluent.

Preparation of Sample Solution:

Take average weight and crush in a mortar by using pestle and weight powder 10 mg equivalent weight of Oxycodone and Naltrexone sample into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask and add about 7mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

Further pipette 0.6ml of the above stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Diluent.

PREPARATION OF DRUG SOLUTIONS FOR LINEARITY:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Oxycodone and Naltrexone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Preparation of Level – I (20 µg/ml of Oxycodone and 10µg/ml of Naltrexone):

Pipette out 0.2ml of the Oxycodone and 0.1ml of the Naltrexone from the above stock solutions in to a 10ml of volumetric flask and dilute the solution. Performes sonication for 10minutes.

Preparation of Level – II (40µg/ml of Oxycodone and 20 µg/ml of Naltrexone):

Pipette out 0.4ml of the Oxycodone and 0.2ml of the Naltrexone from the above stock solutions in to a 10ml of volumetric flask and dilute the solution. Performes sonication for 10minutes.

Preparation of Level – III (60µg/ml of Oxycodone and 30µg/ml of Naltrexone):

Pipette out 0.6ml of the Oxycodone and 0.3ml of the Naltrexone from the above stock solutions in to a 10ml of volumetric flask and dilute the solution. Performes sonication for 10minutes.

Preparation of Level – IV (80µg/ml of Oxycodone and 40 µg/ml of Naltrexone):

Pipette out 0.8ml of the Oxycodone and 0.4ml of the Naltrexone from the above stock solutions in to a 10ml of volumetric flask and dilute the solution. Performes sonication for 10minutes.

Preparation of Level – V (100µg/ml of Oxycodone and 50µg/ml of Naltrexone):

Pipette out 1.0ml of the Oxycodone and 0.5ml of the Naltrexone from the above stock solutions in to a 10ml of volumetric flask and dilute the solution. Performe sonication for 10minutes.

Procedure:

Inject each level into the chromatographic system and measure the peak area.

Plot a graph of peak area versus concentration (on X-axis concentration and on Y-axis Peak area) and calculate the correlation coefficient.

PRECISION

REPEATABILITY

Preparation of Oxycodone and Naltrexone Product Solution for Precision:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Oxycodone and Naltrexone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.6ml of the above Oxycodone and 0.3ml of the Naltrexone stock solutions into a 10ml

volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Diluent.

The standard solution was injected for five times and measured the area for all five injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of five replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

INTERMEDIATE PRECISION:

To evaluate the intermediate precision (also known as Ruggedness) of the method, Precision was performed on different days by maintaining same conditions.

Procedure:

DAY 1:

The standard solution was injected for six times and measured the area for all six injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of six replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

DAY 2:

The standard solution was injected for six times and measured the area for all six injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of six replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

Accuracy:

For preparation of 50% Standard stock solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Oxycodone and Naltrexone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.3ml of the above Oxycodone and 0.15ml of the Naltrexone stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Diluent.

For preparation of 100% Standard stock solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Oxycodone and Naltrexone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.6ml of the above Oxycodone and 0.3ml of the Naltrexone stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Diluent.

For preparation of 150% Standard stock solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Oxycodone and Naltrexone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Procedure:

Inject the Three replicate injections of individual concentrations (50%, 100%, 150%) were made under the optimized conditions. Recorded the chromatograms and measured the peak responses.

Calculate the Amount found and Amount added for Oxycodone and Naltrexone and calculate the individual recovery and mean recovery values.

ROBUSTNESS:

The analysis was performed in different conditions to find the variability of test results. The following conditions are checked for variation of results.

For preparation of Standard solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Oxycodone and Naltrexone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Effect of Variation of flow conditions:

The sample was analyzed at 0.9 ml/min and 1.1 ml/min instead of 1ml/min, remaining conditions are same. 10 μ l of the above sample was injected and chromatograms were recorded

Effect of Variation of mobile phase organic composition:

The sample was analyzed by variation of mobile phase i.e. Acetonitrile: Water was taken in the ratio and 80:20, 70:30 instead of 75:25, remaining conditions are same. 10 μ l of the above sample was injected and chromatograms were recorded.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Trails

Trail 1:

Column : Symmetry C18
(4.6 \times 250mm) 5 μ
Column temperature : Ambient
Wavelength : 285nm
Mobile phase ratio :
Methanol:Water(10:90 v/v)
Flow rate : 1ml/min
Injection volume : 10 μ l
Run time : 10minutes

Figure 1: chromatogram for trail 1

Table 3: peak results for trail 1

S.No	Peak Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate count
	Oxycodone	2.678	215471	38742	1.6	745

Observation:

In this trial it shows less plate count and improper separation of two peaks in the chromatogram. so its required more trials to obtain good peaks.

Trail 2:

Column : ODS C18 (4.6 \times 250mm) 5 μ
Column temperature : 30 $^{\circ}$ C
Wavelength : 285nm
Mobile phase ratio : Methanol:Water(85:15 v/v)
Flow rate : 0.5ml/min
Injection volume : 10 μ l
Run time : 8minutes

Figure 2: chromatogram for trail 2

Table 4: peak results for trail 2

S. No	Peak name	Rt	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP plate count
1	Oxycodone	5.623	46523	29816	1.8	1937
2	Naltrexone	6.571	5366	1947	1.6	1183

Observation:

In this trail it shows improper separation of two peaks, shows less plate count and improper baseline in the chromatogram. Its required more trails to get optimized peaks.

Trail 3:

Column : ODS C18 (4.6×250mm) 5μ
 Column temperature : 30°C
 Wavelength : 285nm
 Mobile phase ratio : Methanol:Water(80:20 v/v)
 Flow rate : 1ml/min
 Injection volume : 10μl
 Run time : 9minutes

Figure 3- chromatogram for trail 3

Table 5: peak results for trail 3

S. No	Peak name	Rt	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP plate count
1	Oxycodone	2.970	38261	17463	2.4	284
2	Naltrexone	3.669	6452	6482	1.9	645

Observation:

From the above chromatogram it was observed that it shows less plate count and more tailing, improper separation of two sample peaks in the chromatogram. More trails required to get optimized chromatogram.

Trail 4 (Optimized chromatogram):

Column : Phenomenex Luna C18 (4.6×250mm) 5 μ
 Column temperature : 35°C
 Wavelength : 285nm
 Mobile phase ratio : Acetonitrile:Water(75:25 v/v)
 Flow rate : 1ml/min
 Injection volume : 10 μ l
 Run time : 7minutes

Figure 4: Optimized Chromatogram (Standard)

Table 6: Optimized Chromatogram (Standard)

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	USP
1	Oxycodone	3.202	2391746	39726	1.2	9028	
2	Naltrexone	5.463	194627	8497	1.1	7398	7.4

Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)**Table 7: Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)**

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	USP Resolution
1	Oxycodone	3.213	2381649	391846	1.2	9472	
2	Naltrexone	5.478	191057	8104	1.1	8936	7.5

Acceptance criteria:

- Resolution between two drugs must be not less than 2
- Theoretical plates must be not less than 2000
- Tailing factor must be not less than 0.9 and not more than 2.
- It was found from above data that all the system suitability parameters for developed method were within the limit.

VALIDATION**Blank:****Fig 7: Chromatogram showing injection -2**

Fig 8: Chromatogram showing injection -3

Fig 9: Chromatogram showing injection -4

Fig 10: Chromatogram showing injection -5

Table 8: Results of system suitability for Oxycodone

S.No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Oxycodone	3.200	2391746	394171	8952	1.2
2	Oxycodone	3.248	2391647	381946	9561	1.2
3	Oxycodone	3.299	2381647	391746	6572	1.2
4	Oxycodone	3.297	2385631	386562	6452	1.2
5	Oxycodone	3.297	2385635	389164	7452	1.2
Mean			2387261			
Std. Dev.			4363.771			
% RSD			0.182794			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2
- The %RSD obtained is within the limit, hence the method is suitable.

Table9: Results of system suitability for Naltrexone

S.No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Naltrexone	5.413	198362	7917	5272	1.1
2	Naltrexone	5.484	197486	7486	6291	1.1
3	Naltrexone	5.405	198354	7859	6184	1.1
4	Naltrexone	5.405	197352	7926	7145	1.1
5	Naltrexone	5.409	198453	7946	6946	1.1
Mean			198001.4			
Std. Dev.			535.1774			
% RSD			0.27029			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2
- The %RSD obtained is within the limit, hence the method is suitable.

SPECIFICITY

The ICH documents define specificity as the ability to assess unequivocally the analyte in the presence of components that may be expected to be present, such as impurities, degradation products, and matrix components. Analytical method was tested for specificity to measure accurately quantitate Oxycodone and Naltrexone in drug product.

Assay (Standard) :

Fig 11: Chromatogram showing assay of standard injection -1

Fig.12: Chromatogram showing assay of standard injection -2

Fig.13: Chromatogram showing assay of standard injection -3

Table 10: Peak results for assay standard**Oxycodone**

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Oxycodone	3.211	2397162	397161	1.2	9472
2	Oxycodone	3.222	2394721	389173	1.2	9745
3	Oxycodone	3.254	2389461	391723	1.2	8917

Naltrexone

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Resolution
1	Naltrexone	5.414	198462	7811	1.1	8492	7.49
2	Naltrexone	5.453	198472	8193	1.1	8916	7.52
3	Naltrexone	5.424	198735	7972	1.1	9372	7.44

Assay (Sample):

Fig 14: Chromatogram showing assay of sample injection-1

Acceptance criteria:

The tailing factor should be less than 2.0 and the number of theoretical plates (N) should be more than 2000.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:**Summary of Validation Parameters for Naltrexone and Oxycodone by Developed RP-HPLC Method**

Parameters	Naltrexone	Oxycodone
Retention Time (min.)	5.463	3.202
Linearity ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	10-50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	20-100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
Correlation Coefficient (r^2)	0.999	0.999
Slope	6548	39080
Y - intercept	454.8	48956
LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	2.5	3.3
LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	7.6	10.1
Repeatability (% RSD) n=6	1.1	0.6
Intraday Precision (% RSD) n=6	0.7	1.6
Interday Precision (% RSD) n=6	0.4	0.2
Accuracy (%)	99.6	99.3

CONCLUSION:

The developed HPLC method offers several advantages such as rapidity, usage of simple mobile phase and easy sample preparation steps. Further, improved sensitivity makes it specific and reliable for its intended use. Hence, this method can be applied for the analysis of pure drug and pharmaceutical dosage forms.

From the present study it can be concluded that the proposed method is simple, sensitive, precise, specific, accurate and reproducible. Results of validation parameters demonstrated that the analytical procedure is suitable for its intended purpose.

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